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Social Institutions on Flexible Learning of Philippine History¹Yosef Eric C. Hipolito

This study determined the contribution of Social Institutions on Flexible Learning of Philippine History in Bulacan Agricultural State College Main Campus during the second semester of Academic Year 2020-2021. With Quantitative method of research as research design and 238 students as respondents of the study, findings disclosed the students agreed that family had contributions on Flexible Learning of Philippine History. Likewise, these respondents agreed that the school had a contribution on their Flexible Learning of the subject. The students agreed that their peers had a contribution on their Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of academic support, personal support, positive interaction and acceptance of new challenges. Similarly, the students agreed that the community where they live had a contribution on their Flexible Learning. In the same manner, they agreed that the state had a contribution on their Flexible Learning. The academic performance of the students in Philippine History was described as “very satisfactory”. Based on the findings of the study, the conclusion that there is a significant relationship between Social Institutions (family, school, peer and state) on Flexible Learning and students’ academic performance in Philippine History was drawn. The higher the support from family, school, peers and state, the higher the grades of the students in Philippine History under the Flexible Learning environment.

Keywords: History, social institutions, education, learning, environment

Introduction

The threat of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Pandemic as a global health concern plagued the year 2020 with unprecedented difficulties in different spheres of human life especially in the education sector. Besides, the global education system experienced the challenges in adapting and transforming with the new and challenging situations to remain in the goal of providing quality education. Regardless of national lockdown and community quarantine to control the transmission of the virus, the “new normal education policy” had been taken.

CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 4, series of 2020 entitled “Guidelines on the Implementation of

Flexible Learning” was formulated in order to have educational protocols for the Academic Year 2020-2021. This required the shift of educational paradigm among Philippine HEIs. The “new normal” set-up necessitates the collaboration among the stakeholders to strengthen the culture of sharing knowledge, resources and best practices. This also contained the flexible teaching and learning options for higher education programs by all private and public HEIs in the country. Correspondingly, CMO No. 4 defines “Flexible Learning” as a pedagogical approach allowing flexibility of time, place and audience, but not solely focused on the use of technology. CHED also clarified

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that the mode of teaching and learning, this may vary depending on the levels of technology, availability of devices, internet connectivity and level of digital literacy as long as it complements to the outcomes-based approach.

Nevertheless, the cases of COVID-19 in the Philippines were still on the rise. As of August 2020, when majority of the HEIs in the country started their Academic Year 2020-2021 with the “new normal” setting, the Department of Health (DOH) had recorded 209,000 total cases in the country. Bulacan Agricultural State College (BASC), as the institution’s academic year started on August 24, 2020, is a local state college without online modalities for the past 69 years since it was established and had opportunity to come up with Flexible Learning for its learners.

The college implemented the BASC Flexible Learning Plan (BASC-FLP) which was approved by the BASC Board of Trustees under BOT Resolution 20-1309 on July 31, 2020. BASC-FLP designated Flexible Learning for the Academic Year 2020-2021 that consist of a teaching strategy which is a combination of “Synchronous/On-Line” classes or the use of desktop, laptops, cellphones and other gadgets to timely meet the discussion of the instructor and “Asynchronous/Off-line” classes or the use of learning packets (e.g., learning modules, activity sheets and learning guides) based from the CHED Curriculum Standards.

Conforming to the previous passages, CHED released a COVID Advisory No. 7 entitled “Guidelines for the Prevention, Control and Mitigation of the Spread of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)” due to Flexible Learning for Academic Year 2020-2021. It emphasized that HEIs should consider their stakeholders in preparation of their continuity and contingency plan for the continuity of education despite the pandemic. Likewise, family, school, peers, community and state are the “Social Institutions” that

can be relied upon the stakeholders of the academe. However, various contributions from different Social Institutions at this time of distance and flexible-laden education shall continuously be assessed.

Amponsah, Milledzi, Ampofo and Gyambrab (2018) and Cadosales, Mastofske, Razonable, Sabroso and Trinidad (2017) affirmed the at-home parental involvement’s significant relationship in monitoring the students’ performance in school including academic achievement, school engagement and socio-emotional adjustment. Giving support to the mentioned assumption, the school also has strong influence in terms of students’ learning as Newchurch (2017) founded that parents and teachers collaborative strategies may represent best practices for developing the whole learner. The study also revealed that schools could use the communication strategies to increase parental support which could increase involvement.

Odoy (2018) expanded the explanation on the assumption that Social Institutions must be assessed in order to see their contribution at this time of distance and flexible-laden education as he insisted that peers may have positive correlation on students’ learning after his study concluded that peer academic support is the best predictor of students’ learning. Further, peer influence had been proven to have an impact on student performance and shown that it has more powerful effects than the immediate family (Ali, Jusof, Ali, Mokhtar and Salamat, 2010).

As an aid to explicate the above premises, the conclusion of Luo, Zhang and Qi (2017) proposed that there is a strong relationship between students’ academic performance and community engagement because it can significantly strengthen students’ sense of membership and can drive students’ eagerness for learning and exploring wider areas.

It is in these premises, the study investigated the Social Institutions present among those citations in a single study in order to assess the extent of their contributions

as educational influencer among students on Philippine History through Flexible Learning.

Objectives

The study focused on determining the contribution of Social Institutions on Flexible Learning of Philippine History in Bulacan Agricultural State College Main Campus during the second semester of Academic Year 2020-2021. In like manner, this study specifically aimed to:

1. Determine the contribution of family in Flexible Learning of Philippine History terms of academic ambition, involvement, time spent to student and guidance.
2. Determine the contribution of school in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of governance, curriculum, teaching-learning and learning assessment.
3. Determine the contribution of peers in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of academic support, personal support, positive interaction and acceptance of new challenges?
4. Determine the contribution of community in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of support for historic sites and structures, promotion in appreciation of history and increase on the awareness of history?
5. Determine the contribution of state in Flexible Learning of Philippine History be in terms of governance and management, quality of teaching and learning and support for students.
6. Describe the students' academic performance in Flexible Learning of Philippine History?
7. Determine if there is a significant relationship between Social Institutions on Flexible Learning and the students' academic performance in Philippine History.

Sampling and location of the study

For the time being due to pandemic times, the researcher performed purposive sampling for the student respondents. This sampling technique is a way of intentionally selecting the respondents based on their ability to give specific theme, concept or phenomenon (Robinson, 2014). For the sample size of student respondents, 30% from the total student population who have Philippine History course during the second semester of Academic Year 2020-2021 were requested to be the respondents of the study.

The researcher conducted the study in Bulacan Agricultural State College (BASC) Main Campus, Barangay Pinaod, San Ildefonso, Bulacan during the second semester of Academic Year 2020-2021. The focus of the study was to determine the contribution of Social Institutions on Flexible Learning of Philippine History in Bulacan Agricultural State College Main Campus during the second semester of Academic Year 2020-2021. In terms of its delimitation, the selection of respondents was limited, since it only covered students in different programs of BASC who were enrolled in Philippine History during the second semester of Academic Year 2020-2021.

Methodology

Research Design and Procedure

This study employed Quantitative method that involved collection, analysis and integration of quantitative (e.g., surveys) type of research.

The researcher personally administered the questionnaire in a form of link from the Google Forms to the group chats of each section via Facebook Messenger. Moreover, the researcher conducted the semi-structured interview through the use of internet generated platform (Google Meet).

In the quantitative data gathering, the utilized questionnaire was composed of a single (1) part which

was adapted from related studies and modified to fit the present study. This part of the questionnaire consists of five (5) sections represented by family, school, peers, community and state that gauged the extent of Social Institutions' contributions on Flexible Learning. Characteristically, each section contains subsections with the Likert scale questions for the survey. Specifically, the Likert scale questions were composed of 5-point scale: 5= *strongly agree*, 4= *agree*, 3= *neutral*, 2= *disagree*, and 1= *strongly disagree*.

As indicated above, the researcher made some revisions and modifications on the adapted questions for the instrument and this action was guided by his research adviser.

Otherwise, the survey questionnaire was pre-tested to the students who were not included as respondents of the study. Pre-testing was done to test the instrument for validity and reliability. Appropriate revisions were made before the actual gathering of data.

For the students' academic performance in Philippine History, the researcher coordinated to all instructors/professors of the said course in order to request for the soft copy of student respondents' numerical ratings for the prelim grading period during the second semester of Academic Year 2020-2021.

Data Analysis Scheme

After retrieving all the responses from Google Forms, these were organized, tallied tabulated, and analyzed using statistical tools.

Descriptive statistics such as range, mean, weighted mean and standard deviation were computed to describe the students' academic performance.

Weighted mean was computed to describe the extent of the involvement of Social Institutions: family,

school, peers, community and state on Flexible Learning.

Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient analysis was applied to determine if significant correlations existed between the dependent (students' academic performance in Philippine History) and independent (extent of the involvement of Social Institutions on Flexible Learning) variables.

Findings

The Contribution of Family in Flexible Learning of Philippine History

The family is one factor that highly influences the students' academic performance, thus the contribution of family in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in this study is measured in terms of the parents' academic ambition, involvement, time spent to students, and guidance.

The perceptions of the students as regards the contribution of family in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of academic ambition, involvement, time spent to students and guidance are presented in Table 1:

<i>Family sub-variables:</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Academic Ambition	3.78	Agree
Involvement	3.75	Agree
Time spent to students	3.34	Neutral
Guidance	3.57	Agree

Results revealed that the students agreed that family's academic ambition, involvement and guidance had contributions on Flexible Learning of Philippine History. However, these respondents agreed nor disagreed that family's time spent to children had

contributions on Flexible Learning of the aforementioned subject.

The result implies that family's academic ambition creates a positive learning environment at home and this can potentially increase the students' academic performance, students need to be responsible about their studies and other types of academic work without the need of too much parental support, the time spent by the parents with their children should be intensified, and the guidance from the parent makes it possible for the children to cope with the new learning environment and makes them use of their time accordingly.

The Contribution of School in Flexible Learning of Philippine History

The task of the school is to deliver quality education despite the current situation and contribution of school in Flexible Learning of Philippine History is measured in terms of its governance, curriculum, teaching-learning, and learning assessment.

Correspondingly, the perceptions of the students as regards the contribution of school in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of governance, curriculum, teaching-learning and learning assessment are presented in Table 2:

<i>School sub-variables:</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Governance	4.13	Agree
Curriculum	4.05	Agree
Teaching-learning	4.25	Agree
Learning	4.20	Agree
Assessment		

The students strongly agreed that the school in terms of teaching-learning had a contribution on their Flexible Learning of Philippine History. Meanwhile,

these respondents agreed that the school in terms of governance, curriculum and learning assessment had a contribution on their Flexible Learning of the subject.

This implies that students had recognized the challenges of the school and the teachers, Flexible Learning Modality ensures that students get enhanced engagement and well-being even without being physically present within the school, Flexible Learning has been successful since it has started due to a world-wide health concern as both the teachers and students adapted to the unusual situation with the help of the school, and students were assessed accordingly as based on the intended learning outcome as based on the Philippine History curriculum which is necessary to ensure the transfer of learning.

The Contribution of Peers in Flexible Learning of Philippine History

The contribution of peers in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in this study is measured through the academic support, personal support, positive interaction, and the acceptance of new challenges provided to the students.

In like manner, the perceptions of the students as regards the contribution of peers in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of academic support, personal support, positive interaction and acceptance of new challenges are presented in Table 3:

<i>Peers sub-variables:</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Academic support	3.89	Agree
Personal support	3.60	Agree
Positive interaction	4.05	Agree
Acceptance of new challenges	4.09	Agree

The students agreed that their peers had a contribution on their Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of academic support, personal support, positive interaction and acceptance of new challenges.

This implies that it is essential that students pick their peers accordingly who will be of help in finishing all necessary tasks and academic related activities, students have developed a positive self-perception and acceptance of their individuality which lowers their level of anxiety allowing them to become more focused on their studies, a positive virtual ambiance and interaction with their classmates on their Philippine History class will help the students to achieve target outcomes and students may get positively involved in supporting their co-students towards learning a subject matter or in attaining target goals.

The Contribution of Community in Flexible Learning of Philippine History

The community support to both the school and students is essential toward the Flexible Learning scheme. In this study, the contribution of community in Flexible Learning of Philippine History is measured in terms of support for historic sites and structures, promotion in appreciation of history and increase on the awareness of history.

The perceptions of the students as regards the contribution of community in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of support for historic sites and structures, promotion in appreciation of history and increase on the awareness of history are presented in Table 4:

<i>Community sub-variables:</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Support for historic sites and structures	3.79	Agree
Promotion in appreciation of history	3.78	Agree
Increase on the awareness of history	3.76	Agree

Likewise, the students agreed that the community where they live had a contribution on their Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of support for historic sites and structures, promotion in appreciation of history and increase on the awareness of history.

This implies that as Community-Based Experiential Learning activities had been introduced, this makes it possible that in our local set up, the community can aid in the learning of the students, the experiences from these interaction and contact with historical sites and artifacts in their community allow the students to fully appreciate and understand the history embedded in each piece or location, and the students can get necessary materials like books, newsletters, or journals, as well as internet connection in the library to aid in their academics.

The Contribution of State in Flexible Learning of Philippine History

The state has the largest contribution to the success of the Flexible Learning education system and this immensely affects the learning of Philippine History. In this study, the contribution of state as represented by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in Flexible Learning of Philippine History is measured in terms of governance and management, quality of teaching and learning, and support for students.

Withal, the perceptions of the students as regards the contribution of CHED in Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of support for historic sites and structures, promotion in appreciation of history and increase on the awareness of history are presented in Table 5:

<i>State sub-variables:</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Governance and Management	4.03	Agree
Quality of teaching and learning	4.02	Agree
Support for students	3.94	Agree

Similarly, the students agreed that the state had a contribution on their Flexible Learning of Philippine History in terms of governance and management, quality of teaching and learning and support for students.

This implies that CHED provides sources for its students to help them learn at home safe on their Philippine History class, through Flexible Learning, CHED has provided an effective curriculum and effective measures for the quality of teaching and learning in Flexible Learning that complies with the standards set by both parents and teachers to assume that quality instruction is provided to their children, and CHED provides support for marginalized communities and gives merit to bright students who deserve scholarships.

The Students’ Academic Performance in Philippine History

Table 6 exhibits the academic performance of the students in Philippine History:

<i>Grade</i>	<i>F (N=90)</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
90 and above	72	30.25	Outstanding (O)
85 – 89	42	17.65	Very Satisfactory (VS)
80 – 84	46	19.33	Satisfactory (S)
75 – 79	78	32.77	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)
74 and below	0	0.00	Did Not Meet Expectations (DNE)
Range		75 – 98	
Mean		85.01	
Verbal Description		Very Satisfactory (VS)	
Standard Deviation		6.82	

It can be noted from the table, almost one-third or 32.77 percent of the students obtained grades that lie within the bracket of 75 to 79. On the other hand, a considerable portion or 30.25 percent of the respondents received grades that lie within the highest bracket of 90 and above. Meanwhile, almost one-fifth or 19.33 percent obtained grades from 80 to 84 while the remaining 17.65 percent got grades from 85 to 89.

Further perusal of the same table reveals that the grades of the students in Philippine History ranged from 75 to 98. The mean was recorded at 85.01 which is verbally described as “very satisfactory”. Meanwhile, the standard deviation which measures the spread of the students’ grades from the mean was registered at 6.82. This result discloses that approximately, 162 students obtained grades within the bracket of 78 to 92. Further, this indicated that the grades of the students in the aforementioned subject are heterogeneous.

Relationship between Social Institutions on Flexible Learning and Students' Academic Performance in Philippine History

In this part of the study, the results of the Pearson product-moment correlations coefficient analysis which was done solely to determine if significant relationship existed between Social Institutions on Flexible Learning and students' academic performance in Philippine History are summarized in Table 7:

<i>Social Institutions</i>	<i>Correlation Value</i>	<i>Probability Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Family	0.164	0.010	Highly Significant
School	0.255	0.000	Highly Significant
Peers	0.217	0.001	Highly Significant
Community	0.008	0.897	Not Significant
State	0.193	0.003	Highly Significant

Legend: Highly Significant: Probability Value ≤ 0.01
Not Significant: Probability Value > 0.05

It can be inferred from the table that a highly significant relationship was found between the Social Institutions on Flexible Learning such as family ($p=0.010$), school ($p=0.000$), peers ($p=0.001$) and state ($p=0.003$) and the academic performance of the students in Philippine History. This highly significant correlation was brought about by the fact that the computed probability values for these variables are smaller than the 0.01 level of significance.

Further examination of the table shows that direct correlation was found between the aforementioned variables as manifested by the positive sign of the correlation values that ranged from 0.164 to 0.255.

This result implies that as the level of support from Social Institutions on Flexible Learning such as family, school, peers and state increases, the level of students' academic performance in Philippine History also increases.

These findings indicate that family, school, peers and the state have a great positive influence on the students' academic performance in Philippine History. Additionally, this implies that in these pandemic days, the support of the Social Institutions play a significant role for the students to attain higher grades in Philippine History.

In accordance to the present findings, Olalekan (2016) affirmed that it is generally observed that peer group has a lot of influence on students' performance in school. This is seen from the role played by the peer group in the life and learning of a child, evidence abound that students feel more comfortable and relaxed among fellow students. A child who is brilliant and surrounded by dull friends would lose interest in learning. On the other hand, a peer group which is highly interested and motivated to study would have a positive effect on a dull member towards learning and stimulate his/her interest on learning.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the conclusion that there is a significant relationship between Social Institutions (family, school, peers and state) on Flexible Learning and students' academic performance in Philippine History was drawn. The higher the support from family, school, peers and state, the higher the grades of the students in Philippine History under the Flexible Learning environment.

References

- Ali, N., Jusof, K., Ali, S., Mokhtar, N. and Salamat, A. S. A. (2010). The factors influencing students' performance at Universiti Teknologi Mara Kedah, Malaysia. *Core*.
https://core.ac.uk/display/236302385?recSetID&fbclid=IwAR1aO41P9Dm0F1LyNew0MBwIPyv0d3cyIheKT_tkKgnLEWxLAI Dj1xrFhGY
- Amponsah, M., Milledzi, E., Twum Ampofo, E., & Gyambrah, M. (2018). Relationship between Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of Senior High School Students: The Case of Ashanti Mampong Municipality of Ghana. *American Journal of Educational Research*. 6. 1-8. 10.12691/education-6-1-1.
- Bulacan Agricultural State College- Flexible Learning Plan (AY 2020-2021) Bulacan Agricultural State College Memorandum No. 18, s. 2020
- Cadosales, R.B.Q., Mastofske, M. M., Razonable, J. Y. C., Sabroso, B. O., Trinidad M.U. (2017). Students' relationship with parents: Basis for an action plan. *Scientific & Academic Publishing*.
http://article.sapub.org/10.5923/j.edu.20170702.02.html?fbclid=IwAR11jxrkp8z_sx89BUUa5BRd5ymJx3o0hXYkmjuk619jMbIveaepbyXtTA
- Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 4 s. 2020.
Commission on Higher Education.
<https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/CMO-No.-4-s.-2020-Guidelines-on-the-Implementation-of-Flexible-Learning.pdf>
- Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 46 s. 2012.
Commission on Higher Education.
<https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CMO-No.46-s2012.pdf>
- Commission on Higher Education: Readings in Philippine History Preliminaries. Retrieved from <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/Readings-in-Philippine-History.pdf>
- COVID-19 cases in PH move past 209,000 with 3,999 new infections (2020, August 24), *CNN Philippines*. Retrieved from <https://www.cnn.ph/news/2020/8/28/covid-19-cases-philippines-209000.html>
- Luo, N., Zhang, M. and Qi, D. (2017). Effects of different interactions on students' sense of community in e-learning environment. *ScienceDirect*.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0360131517301926>
- Odoj, J. (2018). Teacher-peer support and learning behavior of high school students. *ResearchGate*.
<file:///C:/Users/user01/Downloads/ResearchGatePDF.pdf>
- Olalekan, A. B. (2016). Influence of peer group relationship on the academic performance of students in secondary schools: A case study of selected secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State. *Global Journal of Human-Social Science*, 16,